

Practice Of Medical Quackery In Nigeria: A Need For Socio-Legal Intervention

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ABSTRACT

The practice of medical quackery in Nigeria is filled with a plethora of death rows and permanent disabilities caused by untrained persons who pretend to be competent in the dispensation of medical advice and treatment whereas their representation is false and misleading. This is an issue of serious concern in the health sector and even the nation at large. Poverty is one of the main reasons for the prevalence of quackery practices and death as the major adverse effect in the healthcare delivery system. This research work examined the numerous devices used by these quacks, the magnitude of dangers they pose to human life and generated possible solutions to the prevailing threat. The research adopted doctrinal method and the finding of this paper revealed that to do away with quackery, standardization of medical service delivery must be stepped up. This needs a very strong political will. The research therefore concluded and recommended that urgent and proactive steps should be taken to curb the harmful practice of medical quackery in Nigeria through tacit professionalism, application of adequate policy and legal regulations, proper educational/media enlightenment and efficient funding, as holistic panacea to the malice of quackery in Nigeria.

Keywords: Medical Quackery, Health Practitioners, Nigeria, Regulatory Body, Alternative Medicine

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The incessant practice of quackery in the healthcare industry is a serious challenge worldwide and it has become a crucial concern for medical industry throughout history. In the healthcare industry, particularly in developing countries, such as Nigeria, a phenomenon known as medical quackery has been a persistent problem, causing harm in various branches of healthcare services.¹ The practice of medical quackery represents the provision and dispensation of false medical advice or treatment. This involves or relates to the unethical practice of promising health-related benefits for which there is little or no scientific basis and the risk that patients may choose to forgo treatments that are more likely to help them.² Medical quackery has been described as anything involving over promotion in the field of health. This includes questionable ideas and questionable products and services regardless of the sincerity of their promoters.³ This suitably describes the present serious problem in Nigeria where the social media are filled with advertisements of “all curing” remedies, promoted by natural and alternative medicine practitioners and nobody seems to question this, essentially, the charlatans.

¹V. Ndububa, ‘Medical Quackery In Nigeria: Why The Silence?’ (2007) 16 (4) *Nigerian Journal Of Medicine*, October-December 313

²Correspondent. “IMA lodges complaint against 25 quack”, Express Health Care Management, Hyderabad (15 July 2002) available at <<http://www.expresshealthcaremgmt.com20020715/hospi5.shtm>> accessed 22 April 2025

³Ibid

The commonest of them all is sex enhancement products which are very harmful. In essence, medical quackery refers to the fraudulent practice of quacks in the medical field claiming to possess the ability and experience to diagnose and treat diseases, and pretending that the medicines or treatments they provide are effective, but it is generally for personal and financial gain.⁴

A person who engages in the practice of medical quackery is referred to as quack, who is better described as a charlatan. This refers to an untrained person who pretends to be a physician and dispenses medical advice and treatment.⁵ It can simply be defined as an unqualified person, who claims medical knowledge or other skills. This can broadly be described as someone who does not have professional qualification, formal registration from a legitimated institution, or required knowledge of a particular branch of medicine but practices in the field of medicine.⁶ The word 'quack', can be a noun, verb or adjective. Whatever form it is used, it simply connotes 'fraud'.⁷ Quacks are fraudsters and charlatans who lack the necessary scientific qualifications, and their actions, driven by greed, often result in detrimental consequences that weaken the entire health system. Medical professionals regularly use the word to discredit anyone whom they disagree with, especially unqualified healers.⁸ Quacks ordinarily are not ethically bound, and are not committed to any ethical conduct.⁹ They have poor professional judgment, skill, discipline and lack of competence. Also they are always motivated by selfishness and avaricious materialism. In the end, quackery pose very serious hazard to the patient.¹⁰

Quackery can be found in every culture and in every given profession. Presently, the practice of quackery is so advanced in healthcare practice because controlled efforts targeted at this menace have been grossly deficient.¹¹ Therefore this research aims to establish the causes and various means used by these quacks, the magnitude of dangers they pose to human life and to put forward reforms or strategies that could curb medical quackery practices which have become prevailing threat in Nigeria.

2.0 Brief History of Quackery

Immemorially, medical quackery has been in existence, especially in Britain and British colonies, including those in North America. between the 16th and 19th centuries where these quacks widely promoted quack medicine (patent medicines) and successfully promoted their medico-surgical abilities and their remedies to a gullible public.¹² A number of them were dubious and dangerous, and played a part in influencing the history of medical practice between 1750 and 1850.¹³ The later years of the 18th century saw an increase in the number of internationally marketed quack medicines, the majority of which were British in origin.¹⁴

Medical quackery in the United States in the early 19th century was often described as “snake oil” and the quacks were termed 'snake oil peddlers’. These quacks would sell their fake products and leave

⁴Ojone M. Quackery in the nursing profession: cause, effect and way out; (July 2016) available at <www.nursingworldnigeria.com/2016/07/quackery-in-the-nursing-profession-cause-effect-and-way-out-by-ojone-matthew-rn-bn-sc-rphn-in-view> accessed 22 April 2025

⁵Uloko LO, Ossai KO. The quack nurse—a ticking time bomb: eradicate quackery, save lives; (May 2018.) available at < <http://www.nursingworldnigeria.com/2018/05/ind2018-the-quack-nurse-a-ticking-time-bomb-eradicate-quackery-save-lives> >accessed 22 April 2025

⁶ Ibid

⁷ Ibid.

⁸V. Ndububa, 'Medical Quackery In Nigeria: Why The Silence?' (2007) 16 (4) *Nigerian Journal Of Medicine, October-December* 313

⁹ Ibid

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ E. Obiesie and S. Obiesie ,Challenges posed by Quacks and Non Professionals in Healthcare delivery in Nigeria' in M. Izunwa and D. Izunwa(eds), *Law and ethics of healthcare*(Onitsha: Great-M Prints & Ideas, 2016) 608

¹² R. Magee, Ouacks: Fakers and Charlatans in Medicine (2002) Mar: 16 *Pharm Hist Aust* 9-11.

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ K. Griffenhagen , B. George, J. Young. “Old English Patent Medicines in America” (1959) *Contributions from the Museum of History and Technology US, National Museum Bulletin, Washington: Smith Sonia Institution* 155 -183

quickly before the falseness of their medicine is discovered.¹⁵ For instance, William Radam in 1880s, sold his concoction that was widely advertised that it could cure all diseases known as Microbe Killer throughout the British Colonies. The Pure Food and Drug Act, enacted in 1906, was a landmark US law aimed at ensuring the safety and quality of food and drugs. It prohibited the adulteration and misbranding of these products in interstate commerce. This was the result of decades of campaigning by both government departments and the medical establishment supported by a number of publishers and journalists.¹⁶

3.0 Medical Quackery In Nigeria

There is Quackery in different forms. This can be seen in virtually all professions in Nigeria and the world at large. Nigerians are contributing largely to the prevalence of quackery in most professions due to their preference to buy cheap articles, goods and or services given their scarce resources and poor mentality.¹⁷ However, medical quackery is prevalent in Nigeria and has brought about seriously adverse effects. Vulnerable and pregnant people are particularly exploited by these quacks who pose as qualified medical doctors/medical personnel. The end result of this desperation is irreparable physical and internal deformity, complication of existing ailment, and in most cases death.¹⁸

A lot of factors have incessantly permitted and perpetuated the practice of medical quackery for an unusual period of time. Such as Poverty, Unemployment, Ignorance or lack of respect for life. Also, lack of adequate healthcare regulation in the country plays a major role in perpetuating this disaster. Medical Quackery appears to be widespread in Nigeria, and it is clear that both the Government and citizens have nothing to offer in checkmating this virus that has formed the basement of the nation's disordered and horrible healthcare delivery system.¹⁹

It is difficult to ascertain the origin of medical quackery in Nigeria but this certainly predated the colonial era when native doctors or traditional healers were the sole health care providers, now known as the alternative medicine practitioners which can be said to be their modern equivalents.²⁰ The birth of the practice of Alternative Medicine or natural health practice has resulted in yet another transformation in quackery and has particularly assumed great popularity lately but the Federal Government seems to turn the other way, in spite of their unsubstantiated, largely placebo 'cures'.²¹ These practitioners often mix native herbal and root remedies with spiritual divinations and incantations and when their treatments failed to obtain the desired results they attribute the failure to the wrath of the gods.²²

Medical quackery is rampant in Nigeria and culprits are cut across the whole strata of medical and health practitioners.²³ Therefore, medical quackery is not limited to herbal medicine practitioners. Many orthodox health professionals are also culprits, their modus operandi range from medical officers feigning as specialists and thus giving substandard care, to other orthodox health professional guilty of playing the doctor's role, such as the pharmacists, medical laboratory scientists, nurses and

¹⁵E. Obiesie and S. Obiesie, Challenges posed by Quacks and Non Professionals in Healthcare delivery in Nigeria' in M. Izunwa and D. Izunwa (eds), Law and ethics of healthcare(Onitsha: Great-M Prints & Ideas, 2016) 608

¹⁶Ibid

¹⁷Ibid

¹⁸Olawale JT. Menace of quackery in nursing profession; (2020) available at < <https://www.nannm.com.ng/download/menace-of-quackery-in-nursing-profession/>> accessed 22 April 2025

¹⁹Ojone M. Quackery in the nursing profession: cause, effect and way out; (July 2016) available at <www.nursingworldnigeria.coma/2016/07/quackery-in-the-nursing-profession-cause-effect-and-way-out-by-ojone-matthew-rn-bn-sc-rphn-in-view> accessed 22 April 2025

²⁰ V. Ndububa, 'Medical Quackery In Nigeria: Why The Silence?' (2007) 16 (4) *Nigerian Journal Of Medicine, October-December* 313

²¹Olawale JT. Menace of quackery in nursing profession; (2020) available at < <https://www.nannm.com.ng/download/menace-of-quackery-in-nursing-profession/>> accessed 22 April 2025

²²Ibid

²³ V. Ndububa, 'Medical Quackery In Nigeria: Why The Silence?' (2007) 16 (4) *Nigerian Journal Of Medicine, October-December* 313

radiographers.²⁴ Thus, the patients receive substandard care and have been defrauded, this is a form of health fraud which entails deliberate deception. This is apparently, cases of commercial medicine and it is nothing short of medical quackery. The alternative medicine practitioners seem to have gained popularity in the past decades in Nigeria because of the relative cheapness of their medications (compared with the increasing cost of obtaining orthodox health care in Nigeria) and also because of their notorious claims of being able to offer cures for virtually every ailment.²⁵ The unskilled health practitioners such as the traditional native doctors, traditional bone setters, patent medicine sellers and Traditional Birth Attendants (TBAs) all fit into this group. They all have one thing in common they never had any formal and regulatory training although most had one form of apprenticeship or the other. They are not under any regulation, they are let loose into the society, perfecting medical quackery.²⁶

The Poor economic status of the society, increase in the cost of standard health services and inadequate supply of legitimate drugs have forcefully pushed people to unverified products and services whose validity and quality have not been confirmed but they are affordable for them.²⁷ The use of counterfeit services and products not only depletes the limited financial resources of patients but also puts their health at risk.²⁸ When people have insufficient information and health literacy and are not knowledgeable enough to distinguish between standard and unauthorized services, they easily fall prey to deceptive advertisements on social media and in society. This leads them to use counterfeit products and services, resulting in harmful consequences.²⁹ As a result, their trust in legitimate healthcare services and products may diminish.³⁰ Furthermore, as quackery becomes more prevalent in the field of health, people may become distrustful of the entire health system and its professionals and they refuse to see them, ultimately leading to a decline in the overall health of the society.³¹

The occurrence of quackery in the healthcare system is significantly influenced by legal causes. Insufficient laws and regulations, coupled with non-deterrent criminal penalties for exploitations, encourage quacks to continue their unethical and unauthorized activities more boldly, ultimately endangering the lives of patients.³² The lack of technical-organizational factors play a significant role in the spread of quackery in the healthcare system. The rapid growth and careless oversight of online pharmacies, as well as the lack of coordination among stakeholders in health system when it comes to preventing, detecting and countering quack medicine, contribute to the expansion of this problem.³³

In essence, medical quackery in Nigeria, involving unqualified individuals falsely claiming to be medical practitioners, poses significant health risks.³⁴ Medical quackery, also known as charlatanism, involves individuals who fraudulently claim to offer medical services or sell products without

²⁴Ibid

²⁵Ibid

²⁶Olawale JT. Menace of quackery in nursing profession; (2020) available at <<https://www.nanmm.com.ng/download/menace-of-quackery-in-nursing-profession/>> accessed 22 April 2025

²⁷Ibid

²⁸Ibid

²⁹Idris AA. Quackery in nursing: the perception and reality (in Kaduna State); (2020) available at <<https://nursesrevolution.com/quackery-in-nursing-the-perception-and-reality-in-kaduna-state-idris-abdul-ahmed/>> accessed 22 April 2025

³⁰Ibid

³¹Bankole A, Adewole IF, Hussain R, Awolude O, Singh S, Akinyemi JO. The incidence of induced abortion in Nigeria. *Int Perspect Sex Reprod Health J.* 2015; 41(4): 170-181(2015) available at <<https://doi.org/10.1363/4117015>> accessed 22 April 2025

³²Olawale JT. Menace of quackery in nursing profession; (2020) available at <<https://www.nanmm.com.ng/download/menace-of-quackery-in-nursing-profession/>> accessed 22 April 2025

³³Bankole A, Adewole IF, Hussain R, Awolude O, Singh S, Akinyemi JO. The incidence of induced abortion in Nigeria. *Int Perspect Sex Reprod Health J.* 2015; 41(4): 170-181(2015) available at <<https://doi.org/10.1363/4117015>> accessed 22 April 2025

³⁴ Ibid

proper credentials or qualifications.³⁵ This includes the promotion of "all-curing" remedies, often through advertising, and the practice of alternative or natural medicine without scientific validation. It is a widespread problem in Nigeria, with reports indicating that many medical outlets such as medical laboratories, hospitals and even some clinics are staffed by unqualified personnel.³⁶ Quackery poses severe health risks, including the potential for misdiagnosis, ineffective or harmful treatments, and the delay or avoidance of appropriate medical care. Patients may be misled into choosing ineffective treatments or therapies that can worsen their condition. It is expected that professional organizations like the Nigeria Medical Association (NMA), The Nigerian Medical and Dental Council (NMDC) and the Medical Laboratory Science Council of Nigeria (MLSCN) should actively work to combat quackery by addressing the problem seriously, enforcing ethical standards, and collaborating with law enforcement.³⁷

4.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Medical quackery in Nigeria, involving unqualified individuals falsely claiming to be medical or health professionals, is a serious issue requiring a multifaceted socio-legal intervention. Hence the following are hereby suggested that:

1. There is need for orientation of medical and health practitioners and medical/ health students in Nigeria that medical or health practice is a calling to serve humanity and not just a means for financial gain or ill-gotten wealth through quackery. Honest service and sound medical or health practice should not be sacrificed for financial gains.
2. Each medical and health practitioner must adhere strictly to his or her job descriptions or duties within his or her specialty that are clearly outlined or spelt out in the Code of Ethics and as such, except in few cases where duties may overlap, all are expected to carry out their duties as described in order to ensure a harmonic and non-disjointed outcome. It simply means that once a professional decides to take over the job descriptions of another professional, becoming a specialist suddenly, a medical quackery has taken place. In essence, there are quacks 'within' and 'without' every profession. For instance, people who have no proper education on the use/administration of drugs should never attempt prescribing or dispensing drugs.
3. There is need for the medical or health practitioners to be constantly educated and updated through training programmes, conferences, seminars, workshops organised by Medical Laboratory Science Council of Nigeria (MLSCN), The Nigerian Medical and Dental Council (NMDC) in collaboration with Nigerian Medical Association or other health practitioners bodies on the inherent dangers and damages of the practice and patronage of quackery.
4. Public Awareness must be raised. This can be achieved through public education, media advocacy and community engagement. Comprehensive campaigns should be launched to educate the public on the dangers of quackery and the importance of seeking legitimate healthcare. Engaging media outlets in public awareness campaigns can reach a wider audience and help debunk myths surrounding alternative medicine. Community leaders and influencers can play a vital role in raising awareness and promoting healthy choices. Addressing poverty and encouraging sound medical practice will therefore largely curtail alternative medicine practice. In addition, the governments at all level should show more commitment in regulating alternative medicine practice. Clandestine practice will, however, continue if the government does not address poverty and improve health care delivery. The media should create a healthy atmosphere and present a clearer picture by reporting incidents of medical quackery and its attendant adverse effects. The media, intellectuals, social service organizations and educated class must be involved in the fight against quackery. Both the

³⁵ E. Obiesie and S. Obiesie, Challenges posed by Quacks and Non Professionals in Healthcare delivery in Nigeria' in M. Izunwa and D. Izunwa (eds), Law and ethics of healthcare(Onitsha: Great-M Prints & Ideas, 2016) 608

³⁶ *ibid*

³⁷ Ojone M. Quackery in the nursing profession: cause, effect and way out; (July 2016) available at <www.nursingworldnigeria.coma/2016/07/quackery-in-the-nursing-profession-cause-effect-and-way-out-by-ojone-matthew-rn-bn-sc-rphn-in-view> accessed 22 April 2025

- public and stakeholders must be constantly educated through conferences, seminars, workshops etc, on the inherent dangers/damages of the practice / patronage of quackery.
5. It is imperative to address socioeconomic issues such as poverty reduction, improved healthcare access and literacy and education. Poverty is a major driver of quackery, as people may turn to cheaper, unproven remedies due to lack of access to affordable, quality healthcare. Investing in primary healthcare facilities and making healthcare more accessible to all citizens can reduce the demand for quackery. Illiteracy can make individuals more susceptible to false claims and misinformation, so improving literacy rates and promoting education is vital.
 6. The Legal Frameworks must be strengthened. The existing laws need to be reviewed and strengthened to address quackery more effectively, including penalties for practitioners caught engaging in illegal practices. Law enforcement agencies need the resources and training to enforce these laws effectively. Clear lines of communication and collaboration are needed to ensure that laws are in line with the needs of the regulatory bodies.
 7. Promoting evidence-based medicine and supporting research into alternative therapies are strongly recommended. Education and public health campaigns should emphasize the importance of evidence-based medicine and discourage the use of unproven or dangerous treatments. While promoting evidence-based medicine, researchers can also explore the potential of legitimate alternative therapies, as long as they are rigorously tested and safe. Hence, there is need for a specific legislation bordering on Alternative/Herbal medicine practice. This will promote our African heritage but only those that stand the test of scientific trials should be encouraged.
 8. There is need for a specific law on Anti-Quackery that will give legal backing to the fight against quackery in the profession to reduce or eradicate medical quackery and substandard practice. This will go a long way to ensure safety of citizens
 9. Efforts to eradicate medical quackery in Nigeria should be part of the executive, judicial and legislative programs. Apparently, there is need for strong political will to implement the existing laws and ensure compliance to set standards.
 10. There is need to strengthen the regulatory bodies through enhanced surveillance. The relevant boards and bodies need to bolster their inspection and enforcement capabilities to identify and crack down on illegal practices. These boards require adequate funding and staff to effectively regulate the medical profession. Also improved collaboration between regulatory bodies, law enforcement, and professional organizations is crucial for tackling quackery. The Nigerian Medical and Dental Council (NMDC) and other relevant health practitioners' regulatory bodies should intensify its disciplinary actions and sanctions on such erring practitioners who display woeful medical or health practices, including medical quackery. If they fail to practice within the limits of their specializations.
 11. There is urgent need for the government to upwardly review the remuneration of doctors and other health professionals. A well paid health professional is less likely to cut corners and resort to quackery.
 12. There is need for proper and adequate funding of the healthcare industry by the government.
 13. There is need to for quality control to ensure that the quality of medical services conform to established medical standards. It will reduce patient complaints about services rendered and enhance reputation of the medical profession. This will eliminate the involvement of unskilled labor in medical practice.

By implementing these socio-legal interventions, Nigeria can make significant strides in combating medical quackery and ensuring that its citizens have access to safe and effective healthcare.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Medical quackery in Nigeria, involving unqualified individuals falsely claiming to be medical or health practitioners, poses significant health risks. Despite this, medical quackery has been incessantly practiced in Nigeria and even many orthodox practitioners are not exempted. The unorthodox health practitioners are having a field day as well. It is painful that the government and other stake holders in

the health care system in the country seem to be helpless, but there can be a way out. The Nigerian Medical and Dental Council and other health practitioners' regulatory bodies should pay more attention to the quality of their professionals than just collecting annual practicing dues. The government and the leadership of Nigeria must change from their present inept leadership where transparency and meritocracy are relegated to the background in favour of nepotism and graft. This has been a major reason for the country remaining poor and poverty promotes both patronage and practice of medical quackery. The need to improve the remunerations and the conditions of service of health professionals cannot be over emphasized. For a good and optimal healthcare delivery system in Nigeria, our political leaders must be sincere to themselves, and to GOD. If the state exercises the right will, quackery will be a thing of history in Nigeria. In other words, a socio-legal intervention approach, combining social awareness campaigns with legal enforcement, is crucial to combat the issue medical quackery. This includes strengthening regulatory bodies, enacting and enforcing relevant laws, and addressing underlying socioeconomic factors that contribute to the problem.